

Supplementary Material

S1. 'Hyperimperialist Exploitation' scenario

Complete storyline:

"[...] [T]he world system continues its trajectory, leading to ever increasing global economic output and environmental degradation, but maintaining intra- and international economic inequality. However, as biophysical limits to growth become ever more evident, the system is forced to depart from its trajectory of global accumulation based on dynamic competition. In Hyperimperialist Exploitation [...] the capitalist elites of the center, with the collaboration of capitalist and political elites of the semiperiphery and periphery, maintain their consumption and power despite the world economy's stagnation and subsequent degrowth, while workers of the center struggle to keep their former lifestyles, and workers of the semiperiphery and periphery increasingly fight for survival as they see their wages stagnate and decline." (Lauer & Llases, 2025)

S2. Sectorial disaggregation in MORDRED

Sector number	Sector description
1	Agriculture, food, beverages
2	Non-energy use of biomass
3	Fossil fuels used for energy
4	Mining
5	Industry not elsewhere classified
6	Recycling industry
7	Services not elsewhere classified
8	Non-energy use of fossil fuels
9	Chemical industry
10	Biomass used for energy
11	Manufacturing
12	Fossil fuel-based electricity
13	Nuclear electricity
14	Hydroelectricity
15	Wind based electricity
16	Biomass and waste based electricity
17	Solar PV electricity
18	Solar thermal electricity
19	Tide, wave and ocean based electricity
20	Geothermal electricity
21	Transport
22	Education
23	Health
24	Waste industry
25	Waste ,recycling' (biogasification & composting) industry

Table S1: Overview of sectoral disaggregation in MORDRED. See Model documentation of MORDRED.

S3. Scenario parametrization

S3.1. Evolution of the A matrix

The target A matrix that is reached by the initial A matrix in 2100 was derived through the following steps.

1. Monetary to energy (E) inputs

Starting from the A matrix for the world in 2019, which is disaggregated into 25 sectors, we converted the numbers contained in the rows of the A matrix representing energy sectors (3,10,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20) (see S2 this Supplementary Material) from economic input per unit of economic output into energy input per unit of economic output. To this end, the original values in the rows corresponding to the energy sectors were multiplied by the energy intensity of the respective sectors.

$$\begin{aligned} a_{3,1...25_E} &= [a_{3,1} * i_3] \quad [a_{3,2} * i_3] \quad \dots \quad [a_{3,25} * i_3] \\ a_{10,1...25_E} &= [a_{10,1} * i_{10}] \quad [a_{10,2} * i_{10}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{10,25} * i_{10}] \\ a_{12,1...25_E} &= [a_{12,1} * i_{12}] \quad [a_{12,2} * i_{12}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{12,25} * i_{12}] \\ a_{13,1...25_E} &= [a_{13,1} * i_{13}] \quad [a_{13,2} * i_{13}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{13,25} * i_{13}] \\ &\vdots \\ a_{20,1...25_E} &= [a_{20,1} * i_{20}] \quad [a_{20,2} * i_{20}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{20,25} * i_{20}] \end{aligned}$$

2. Introduction of the process (P) efficiency coefficient.

To reflect energy efficiency improvements through the improvements of economic processes throughout the economy, all the biophysical inputs in the A matrix are multiplied by the factor $\alpha_{processes}$ which in the scenario parametrization takes the value 0.95, i.e. reflects a 5% increase in all economic processes requiring energy.

$$\begin{aligned} a_{3,1...25_{E,P}} &= [a_{3,1E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad [a_{3,2E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{3,25E} * \alpha_{processes}] \\ a_{10,1...25_{E,P}} &= [a_{10,1E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad [a_{10,2E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{10,25E} * \alpha_{processes}] \\ a_{12,1...25_{E,P}} &= [a_{12,1E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad [a_{12,2E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{12,25E} * \alpha_{processes}] \\ a_{13,1...25_{E,P}} &= [a_{13,1E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad [a_{13,2E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{13,25E} * \alpha_{processes}] \\ &\vdots \\ a_{20,1...25_{E,P}} &= [a_{20,1E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad [a_{20,2E} * \alpha_{processes}] \quad \dots \quad [a_{20,25E} * \alpha_{processes}] \end{aligned}$$

3. Replacement (R) of inefficient renewable energy technologies

In the target A matrix the electricity coming from biomass, solar thermal, tide and geothermal is assumed to be substituted by hydroelectricity, solar PV and wind based electricity, given the inferior performance of the former compared to the latter (e.g. De Castro, 2023; De Castro et al.,

2011). Thus, the values in the respective rows are set to zero. The inputs from wave/tidal energy are added to hydroelectricity; the inputs from geothermal electricity are added to wind electricity; the values from solar thermal and bioelectricity are added to electricity from solar PV.

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{14,1...25_{E,P,R}} &= [a_{14,1_{E,P}} + a_{19,1_{E,P}}] [a_{14,2_{E,P}} + a_{19,2_{E,P}}] \dots [a_{14,25_{E,P}} + a_{19,25_{E,P}}] \\
a_{15,1...25_{E,P,R}} &= [a_{15,1_{E,P}} + a_{20,1_{E,P}}] [a_{15,2_{E,P}} + a_{20,2_{E,P}}] \dots [a_{15,25_{E,P}} + a_{20,25_{E,P}}] \\
a_{16,1...25_{E,P,R}} &= [0] [0] \dots [0] \\
a_{17,1...25_{E,P,R}} &= [a_{17,1_{E,P}} + a_{16,1_{E,P}} + a_{18,1_{E,P}}] [a_{17,2_{E,P}} + a_{16,2_{E,P}} + a_{18,2_{E,P}}] \dots [a_{17,25_{E,P}} + a_{16,25_{E,P}} + a_{18,25_{E,P}}] \\
a_{18,1...25_{E,P,R}} &= [0] [0] \dots [0] \\
a_{19,1...25_{E,P,R}} &= [0] [0] \dots [0] \\
a_{20,1...25_{E,P,R}} &= [0] [0] \dots [0]
\end{aligned}$$

4. Greening (G): Replacement of fossil and nuclear through renewable energy

The demand for fossil electricity in the target A matrix is assumed to decline by the factor α_{ff} (=0.9 in the scenario parametrization) while the demand for nuclear electricity is assumed to decline by the factor α_{nuc} (=0.4). At the same time, the demand for hydro, wind and solar PV electricity is assumed to grow by the same factor, i.e. fossil and nuclear electricity are substituted to equal parts by hydro, wind and solar PV.

Thus, the new input coefficients are:

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{12,1...25_{E,P,R,G}} &= [a_{12,1_{E,P,R}} * (1 - \alpha_{ff})] [a_{12,2_{E,P,R}} * (1 - \alpha_{ff})] \dots [a_{12,25_{E,P,R}} * (1 - \alpha_{ff})] \\
a_{13,1...25_{E,P,R,G}} &= [a_{13,1_{E,P,R}} * (1 - \alpha_{nuc})] [a_{13,2_{E,P,R}} * (1 - \alpha_{nuc})] \dots [a_{13,25_{E,P,R}} * (1 - \alpha_{nuc})] \\
a_{14,1...25_{E,P,R,G}} &= \left[a_{14,1_{E,P,R}} + \frac{a_{12,1_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{ff} + a_{13,1_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{nuc}}{3} \right] \dots \left[a_{12,25_{E,P,R}} + \frac{a_{12,25_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{ff} + a_{13,25_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{nuc}}{3} \right] \\
a_{15,1...25_{E,P,R,G}} &= \left[a_{15,1_{E,P,R}} + \frac{a_{12,1_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{ff} + a_{13,1_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{nuc}}{3} \right] \dots \left[a_{15,25_{E,P,R}} + \frac{a_{12,25_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{ff} + a_{13,25_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{nuc}}{3} \right] \\
a_{17,1...25_{E,P,R,G}} &= \left[a_{17,1_{E,P,R}} + \frac{a_{12,1_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{ff} + a_{13,1_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{nuc}}{3} \right] \dots \left[a_{17,25_{E,P,R}} + \frac{a_{12,25_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{ff} + a_{13,25_{E,P,R}} * \alpha_{nuc}}{3} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

5. Electrification (El)

We identified the sectors that (a) do not already have high rates of electric input compared to energy inputs from other energy types, and (b) have some technical potential to be electrified. Those sectors have the numbers 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 17, 21, 25.

α_{el} denotes the share of energy inputs that is assumed to be replaced by electric energy in 2100 and is set to 0.2. It is assumed that the electricity is covered by an increase in the electricity produced by wind and solar PV (both are assumed to cover half of the additional electricity). Furthermore, it is assumed that in the process of electrification the process efficiency is also improved by a factor (α_{elp}) which in the scenario quantification is optimistically set to 0.5. Thus,

the increase in electricity from wind (sector 15) and solar PV (sector 17) is smaller than the reduction of non-electric energy, i.e. fossil energy (sector 3) and bioenergy (sector 10).

For the columns of the A matrix corresponding to the sectors with electrification potential, the rows corresponding to non-electric energy input and electric input were modified accordingly:

$$a_{3,1...25_{E,P,R,G,El}} = \dots \left[a_{3,3_{E,P,R,G}} * (1 - \alpha_{el}) \right] \left[a_{3,5_{E,P,R,G}} * (1 - \alpha_{el}) \right] \dots \left[a_{3,25_{E,P,R,G}} * (1 - \alpha_{el}) \right]$$

$$a_{10,1...25_{E,P,R,G,El}} = \dots \left[a_{10,3_{E,P,R,G}} * (1 - \alpha_{el}) \right] \left[a_{10,5_{E,P,R,G}} * (1 - \alpha_{el}) \right] \dots \left[a_{10,25_{E,P,R,G}} * (1 - \alpha_{el}) \right]$$

$$a_{15,1...25_{E,P,R,G,El}} = \dots \left[a_{15,3_{E,P,R,G}} + (a_{3,3_{E,P,R,G}} + a_{10,3_{E,P,R,G}}) * \alpha_{el} * \alpha_{el_p} \right] \dots \left[a_{15,25_{E,P,R,G}} + (a_{3,25_{E,P,R,G}} + a_{10,25_{E,P,R,G}}) * \alpha_{el} * \alpha_{el_p} \right]$$

$$a_{17,1...25_{E,P,R,G,El}} = \dots \left[a_{17,3_{E,P,R,G}} + (a_{3,3_{E,P,R,G}} + a_{10,3_{E,P,R,G}}) * \alpha_{el} * \alpha_{el_p} \right] \dots \left[a_{17,25_{E,P,R,G}} + (a_{3,25_{E,P,R,G}} + a_{10,25_{E,P,R,G}}) * \alpha_{el} * \alpha_{el_p} \right]$$

6. Target A Matrix in monetary values

Finally, we convert the energy inputs back to monetary inputs by dividing the values by the energy intensities.

$$a_{3,1...25_{final}} = \left[a_{3,1_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_3} \right] \left[a_{3,2_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_3} \right] \dots \left[a_{3,25_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_3} \right]$$

$$a_{10,1...25_{final}} = \left[a_{10,1_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_{10}} \right] \left[a_{10,2_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_{10}} \right] \dots \left[a_{10,25_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_{10}} \right]$$

$$\vdots$$

$$a_{20,1...25_{final}} = \left[a_{20,1_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_{20}} \right] \left[a_{20,2_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_{20}} \right] \dots \left[a_{20,25_{E,P,R,G,El}} * \frac{1}{i_{20}} \right]$$

S3.2. Evolution of final demand

The consumption shares that vary according to consumption per capita, the sectoral shares in government demand and the sectoral shares in Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) follow the changes made in the A matrix regarding the replacement (R) of inefficient electricity technologies, the greening (G) of the electricity mix and the electrification of energy demand (El). Since final demand is not engaged in production activity, the process efficiency factor was not applied.

Since the consumption vector stays constant above a threshold value of 24,673 € annual per capita consumption, the share of food expenditures could be overestimated in scenarios in which a significant proportion of the households have a consumption greater than this value. Thus, we correct the consumption vector for richest households by multiplying the share in household expenditures for the food sector by 0.5 and by adding this amount to the expenditure share for services.

S3.3. Evolution of labor, capital and land intensity

Labor productivity of the world in 2100 approximates labor productivity of the center in 2019 in all sectors as in the absence of biophysical restrictions to economic growth economic development in the Global South would likely increase the labor productivity in these regions and rise average global productivities. As sectoral labor productivity levels evolve exogenously in the scenario simulation, labor productivity could be overestimated starting from the second half of the simulation, given that sectoral productivities continue to improve although economic development in the Global South reverts its historical direction and economic development in the Global North stagnates.

Capital intensity is given as capital-stock-to-output ratio and capital productivity as output-to-stock ratio. It is assumed that, *ceteris paribus*, in 2100 capital productivity increases by 20% which - like the labor productivity assumption - is optimistic and is a factor contributing to an overestimation of the material and energy efficiency performance of the economy.

The target capital intensity in 2100 is given as:

$$Capital\ intensity_{2100_s} = \frac{1}{\frac{output_s}{capital\ stock_s} * 1.2} = \frac{5}{6} * \frac{capital\ stock_s}{output_s}$$

The last optimistic assumption concerns future land productivities. While the intensity of land demand for infrastructure depends on household demands and is assumed to remain constant, the land productivity of all other land types, including the land productivity of renewable energies and of the forestry sector, is assumed to grow by 2.25% annually, a very favorable development that is significantly higher than what would be achieved if the world merely approached the higher land productivities of the Center in 2019. Furthermore, this development is assumed to continue even in the post-BAU phase. Adopting less optimistic assumptions would very likely lead to a stagnation of global output much earlier in time.

Other scenario variables not explained in this Supplementary Material either remain constant during the simulations or take standard values chosen for the basic calibration of MORDRED given that they are not significant for the research questions addressed in this paper, and, thus, are excluded from the scope of the analysis.

S4. Consumption ratios

Fig. S 1: a) Evolution of intraregional consumption per capita ratios for the three world regions (consumption per capita of the richest 20% divided by the consumption per capita of the poorest 30% in a region). Red line: center, yellow line: semiperiphery, blue line: periphery. b) Evolution of interregional consumption per capita ratios. Grey line: the richest 20% of the center compared to poorest 30% of the periphery; blue line: the richest 20% of the center compared to the richest 20% of the semiperiphery; black line: the richest 20% of the semiperiphery compared to the richest 20% of the periphery).

S5. Alternative scenario runs

We have specified four alternative scenario runs — scenario variations (SV) 1 to 4 — to test the robustness of the observed dynamics in the base run presented in the main text and to gain additional insights about potential model dynamics under different scenario assumptions.

In SV1, we assume a higher level of greenhouse gas emission reductions. Therefore, the greenhouse gas intensity of non-combustion related emissions is exogenously reduced by 20% between 2019 and 2100 while in the Baseline the intensity remains constant.

In SV2, we make more pessimistic assumptions about the sensitivity of the climate system to anthropogenic pressure. Thus, we activate climate feedbacks within the climate system that lead to an increase in natural greenhouse gas emissions as global temperatures rise.

In SV3, we make more pessimistic assumptions about future exogenous growth in sectoral labor productivities, which only reach 80% of the center's 2019-productivity-levels by 2100.

In SV4, we modify the allocation priorities in the model to simulate a lower degree of divergence in consumption when scarcity issues arise.

We find that the dynamics observed in the base run presented in the main article are broadly similar to those produced in the scenario variations, although they differ in timing and magnitude. In SV2, collapse dynamics occur approximately one decade earlier than in the

baseline while in the remaining scenario variations, they appear about one decade later than in the baseline (Fig. S 2, Fig. S 3).

The higher level of climate mitigation in SV1 leads to higher maximum output levels and maximum per capita consumption levels in all social classes, a lower increase in temperatures and a stabilization of the population of the periphery at a higher level than in the other scenarios.

Conversely, the higher climate sensitivity in SV2 results in an earlier stagnation and decline of world output and consumption at a lower level, and – due to the spread of extreme poverty – an earlier decline in the population of the semiperiphery and the periphery.

The lower labor productivity in SV3 is linked to lower maximum levels of output and consumption, a lower increase in global average temperature, and a delay in the break-down of the world economy compared to the baseline simulation.

Last, the lower degree of divergence in SV4 prolongs the time period during which the scenario is stable and leads to somewhat smoother declines in world output and the consumption of the poorer classes. However, when the system finally collapses, the consumption level of the center falls to a lower level than in the other scenario simulations. In fact, the loss in consumption of the poorest class in the center is so strong that critical levels for survival are reached, and, thus, the population of the center collapses as well. Hence, less divergence delays the breakdown of the system but a longer period of overshoot and correspondingly higher levels of global warming ultimately results in higher consumption losses for the richest classes, which in SV proves catastrophic for the center.

Thus, the key dynamics discussed in the article can also be observed in alternative ‘divergence and polarization’ scenarios that differ in important scenario variables while maintaining the underlying logic of the scenario storyline, i.e. a strong cost-shifting from richer to poorer classes and an absence of policies aimed at a reduction of the most extreme forms of poverty. It is the former that creates critical risks to system instability, and the latter that triggers the demographic collapse.

Fig. S 2: Evolution of consumption per capita of all social classes sustained by the world economy in the four scenario variations (SV) and the baseline (red line).

Fig. S 3: Evolution of a) the population in the center b) the population in the semiperiphery, c) the population in the periphery, d) global annual output, e) global warming with respect to 1850 in the four scenario variations and the baseline (red line).